

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

A NEW APPROACH TO THE SYNTHESIS OF ADAMANTYL-CONTAINING HETEROCYCLES

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Abstract

For the first time, methods for the synthesis of adamantyl-containing amidoalkylating agents based on Schiff bases have been developed. These synthons have been used to synthesize a variety of nitrogen-containing heterocycles. The following adamantyl-containing heterocycles and their derivatives were obtained: alkyl-5-thioxo-3-thia-4,6,7a-triazaindene, 1,3,5-hexahydrotriazine system, 2-imidazolin-5-one, 1,2,4-triazine, triazepinones, 3-oxotetrahydroisoquinolines, derivatives of dihydroisoindole and others.

Keywords: *Triazepines, 2-aminothiazole, natural amino acids, imidoyl chlorides, phosphorus pentachloride.*

Introduction.

The chemistry of derivatives of nitrogenous heterocycles attracts the attention of chemists, since these compounds are of great scientific and practical importance. They are used in the production of polymer materials, dyes, medicines, insecticides, herbicides, and plant growth regulators.

Heterocyclic compounds occupy a significant place among physiologically active substances. A special place among them is occupied by compounds having an adamantyl radical as a substituent. The specific physiological activity of such heterocycles is known from many examples. However, their availability varies quite significantly, which is determined by the method of synthesis.

Among the fused heterocycles, the most famous are indoles, quinazolines, and benzodiazepines. Pharmacophores based on them are widely presented in the literature. Condensed systems with a seven-membered heterocycle are much less common.

Nevertheless, among them, compounds have been identified that exhibit antitumor and antiviral properties, are used as psychotropic drugs [1].

However, many heterocyclic compounds are difficult to prepare, which limits their scope of application. Therefore, the search for new regioselective heterocyclizations based on available reagents is very relevant. Such reagents currently include various adamantyl-

containing compounds and amidoalkylating agents based on them.

Particular attention should be paid to the presence of an adamantyl fragment in the composition of amidoalkylating agents. Pharmacologists are well aware that the presence of such a fragment can impart unique pharmacophoric properties to compounds.

Aim.

The development of new methods for the synthesis of adamantyl-containing heterocycles is an urgent problem of organic synthesis and, therefore, is the subject of this study. We also wanted to test the possibility of using an adamantyl-containing imidoalkylating reagent in the condensation reaction.

Materials and methods.

The reagents of the company Lancaster were used. IR spectra were obtained on a Specord 751R spectrometer for samples in KBr tablets containing 0.25% of the substance. Or in a thin film, layer thickness 0.6 mm. PMR spectra were taken on Bruker AVANCE III HD (400 MHz). GLC analysis was carried out on a ЦВЕТ-500 device, glass column 2000x3 mm, 15% Apiezon L on Inerton N-AW-HMDS carrier, temperature 150-260°C (10 deg/min), carrier gas – helium (40 ml/min). The mixtures were separated by column chromatography on Silicagel L 40/100 sorbent. Chromatomass spectra are measured on the Hewlett-Packard 5890-II

device with a detector MSD 59771A (capillary 30 m, HP-1, 100-250 °C, 10° / min).

The structure of intermediate and final compounds was proved by IR and ¹H, ¹³C NMR spectrometry and mass spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

Condensation of adamantylisothiocyanate with 2-aminotiazol.

Thiazole derivatives show pharmacological activity: antimicrobial antiviral and antihistamines, diuretics and mitodepressants.

- 1: R₁=R₂=R₃=H; 2: R₁=R₂=H, R₃=CH₃; 3: R₁=H, R₁=R₃=CH₃;
4: R₁=R₂=R₃=CH₃; 5: R₁=R₂=H, R₃=CH₃, p-Ph

Example of synthesis of condensed 1,3,5-hexahydrotriazine system using adamantylcontaining iminoalkylating reagent.

1,3,5-Triazines are usually most readily prepared by reactions of 2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine. However, the ring system can also be synthesized by condensation reactions.

The starting compound for the synthesis of the imidoalkylating reagent (7) was Schiff's base (6), which

was obtained from benzaldehyde and aniline by a standard procedure. After isolation, imine (6) was treated with 1-adamantylacetic acid chloranhydride in dichloroethane. Equimolar amounts of 2-aminoimidazole as a condensation component, triethylamine and dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) were added to product (7) without isolation. The reaction took place at reflux for 2 hours. The yield of the condensation product (8) was 43%.

The method developed by us for the synthesis of compound (8) is a separate example of the synthesis of such systems. Wide possibilities for obtaining a family of similar compounds are opened by varying the substituents in the starting imide, adamantyl radical, and amine condensation component.

Cyclization of 1-adamantylglycine derivatives.

The intramolecular cycles discussed in this section necessarily involve a functional substituent in the α -position to the adamantium nucleus and proceed, in most cases, with the participation of the amide group.

As can be seen from the scheme, treatment of acylated 1-adamantylglycine (9) with dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) in dry chloroform

leads to oxazolone (10). Cleavage of the latter with various nucleophiles: ammonia, primary and secondary amines, hydroxylamine, hydrazine and its organic derivatives gives derivatives of α -acylaminocarboxylic acid (11). Upon dehydration of synthons (11), depending on their structure and condensation conditions, derivatives of 2-imidazolin-5-one (13) and 1,2,4-triazine (12) are obtained. The yields of compounds (10), (12), (13) were 85%, 73%, 77%, respectively.

Another important synthon derived from 1-adamantylglycine is the Schiff base (14). The amidoalkyl-atin reagent (15) was obtained from it by treatment with monochloroacetic acid chloride in toluene. Without isolation, it was converted to an oxy derivative (16). Oxazolone (17) was obtained by azeotropic distillation of methanol in 84% yield. The addition of triethylamine to a solution of compound (17) in benzene, followed by reflux for 3 hours, resulted in heterocycle closure (18) in 69% yield [2].

The outputs of the target products were: for $R_2 = \text{Ad}$ - 78%, AdCH_2 - 84%, AdCH_2CH_2 - 87%, $R_2 = \text{AdCH}_2$ - 66%.

A convenient method of synthesis of potentially physiologically active adamantyl-containing 3-oxotetrahydroisoquinolins has been developed.

Synthesis of adamantanecontaining derivatives of dihydroisoindole.

Heterocyclic compounds occupy a significant place among physiologically active substances. Among the fused heterocycles, the most famous are indoles, quinazolines, benzodiazepines. Pharmacophores based on them are widely represented in the literature.

To obtain the structures presented in the scheme, the method of imidoalkylating agents - Schiff bases (24) was used [1]. The latter were synthesized on the basis of benzaldehyde and benzylamine. To obtain acyliminium salt (25), 1-adamantylacetic acid chloranhydride was used.

Heating a solution of an acyliminium salt in a solution of dichloroethane in the presence of triethylamine led with a yield of 58% to an isoindole derivative - N- [1-adamantylmethylcarboxy] -2-phenyldihydroisoindole (26).

Examples of the synthesis of heterocycles based on adamantyl-containing imidoalkylating reagents.

Syntheses were carried out according to standard procedures. Some of them are given in the monograph [2].

The scheme shows the scheme for the synthesis of imidoalkylating reagents (32) and (34) [1]. Treatment

of (6) with dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) in dry chloroform gave oxazolone (33) in 87% yield. Similarly, heterocycle (35) was obtained from amide (34) in 85% yield.

The following scheme shows the synthesis of heterocycle (40) from reagent (39) [1]. The concerted alkylation proceeds by refluxing in dry toluene in the

presence of an equimolar amount of triethylamine. The yield of product (40) was 91%.

The use of amine (41) and its homologues as components for the preparation of Schiff bases (42) and then the N-acylated precursor (43) [1] made it possible

to synthesize seven-membered condensed lactam (44) in 49% yield.

Of particular interest is the Schiff base (46), since it allows one to obtain hard-to-reach heterocycles (47) in one step. The substituents on the parent amine must be electron withdrawing groups to ensure consistent

orientation during alkylation. The yields of heterocycles (47), depending on the substituent, were 57%, 63%, and 60%, respectively.

The following two examples show the introduction of the pharmacophore group of 1-adamantylglycine into heterocycles (51) and (55). Yields (51) and

(55), however, were mediocre at 39% and 43%, respectively.

Conclusions

Methods for the synthesis of amidoalkating reagents containing an adamantane radical have been developed for the first time. On their basis, various nitrogen-containing heterocycles have been synthesized, which may be of interest as physiologically active substrates.

References:

1. Komodzinski K. Biological evaluation of an imidazole-fused 1,3,5-triazepinone nucleoside and its photochemical generation via a 6-azidopurine modified oligonucleotide. // *Tetrahedron Letters*. – 2013. – 54. – P. 3781-3784.
2. Драч Б.С., Броварец В.С., Смолий О.Б. // Синтезы азотсодержащих гетероциклических

соединений на основе амидоалкилирующих агентов/ Киев.: Наукова думка, 1992.- 174 С.

3. Ingersoll A.W., Babcock S. H. Hippuric acid // *Organic Syntheses, Coll.* – Vol. 2, p. 328 (1942); Vol 12, p. 40 (1932).

4. Krasutsky P.A., Novicova M.I., Semenova I.G. *Chim. pharm.* 2., 1985. v.19, №7, pp. 825-829.

5. Драч Б.С., Миськевич Г.Н. Взаимодействие метилового эфира β,β -дихлор- α -бензамидоакриловой кислоты с пятихлористым фосфором // *Журнал органической химии*. – 1978. – Т. 14, №5. – С. 943-947.

6. Venkov A.P., Mollov N.M. // *Synthesis*. – 1982. - №3. – P.216-217.